

ROSIE

D9.1: Data Management Plan v1.0

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1 Data Summary

Note that this is the first version of the Data Management Plan of ROSiE. The DMP will be updated when necessary.

The overall aim of the ROSiE project is to provide guidance and tools related to the RE/RI, legal, and social implications and challenges inherent in OS, thereby facilitating the integration of RE/RI as a structural component of OS in Europe. Specifically, this translates into the following specific objectives and outputs:

No	Specific Objective	Time-bound, Measurable Outputs
1	EXPLORE: Map, examine, evaluate, and provide a conceptual and normative framework on the RE/RI dimensions of OS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 3 reports/articles on the RE/RI implications and challenges • 1 suggested framework for epistemic-ethical challenges • 1 workshop • Collect 10 OS case studies plus 1 for the global dimension • (Recommendations for guidance on RE/RI aspects of OS)
2	EXPLORE: Map, examine, evaluate, and provide guidance on the social and legal dimensions of OS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 reports/articles on the social and legal implications and challenges of OS • Recommendations on legal and social aspects of OS
3	EXPLORE and ENGAGE: With relevant stakeholders, identify and address gaps of current practices of OS in different research disciplines	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • List of stakeholders • 2 reports/articles on Stakeholder Forum activities and interview results • Recommendations from the analysis of the consultation process
4	EXPLORE and ENGAGE: Consolidate relevant knowledge on RE/RI from related EU-funded projects to make sure that their outputs are taken into account	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Launch and coordinate the cross-SwafS Community of Practice to consolidate knowledge beyond the ROSiE consortium • Disseminate ROSiE outcomes to existing EU knowledge-sharing platforms
5	GUIDE: Create a detailed strategic policy assessment for promoting responsible OS, to provide balanced operational guidelines for relevant stakeholders and complement the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (ECoC) on RE/RI within the OS framework	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report on existing policies and guidelines • Strategic policy paper for promoting responsible OS • Policy document complementing the ECoC
6	EXPLORE and GUIDE: Examine, evaluate, and provide guidance on the readiness of existing OS platforms to handle sensitive personal data	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report on the mapping and analysis of European and national infrastructures promoting responsible OS

7	EQUIP: Develop a knowledge hub that can support all research disciplines in actively pursuing open approaches in science and research while complying with legal frameworks and ethical standards	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ROSIE knowledge hub
8	EQUIP: Develop training materials with and for researchers and citizen scientists for acquiring skills required for responsible practice of OS	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Responsible OS 2day-training materials
9	ENGAGE: Effectively communicate with ROSIE stakeholders, proactively engage target audiences, and disseminate project outcomes as widely as possible	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 2 promotional videos • ROSIE logo • ROSIE website • Social media presence (Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn) • 1 conference

Several of ROSIE outputs would require gathering of data, which may be in the form of desk research through literature review, stakeholder consultation meetings, or co-creational workshops.

There are two types of data that ROSIE will collect: first, there will be literature review, thus data from published articles and/or grey literature. Second, personal data from stakeholder consultation meetings and workshops. Stakeholders could come from the Stakeholder Forum created by WP3 or from separate invites, depending on what the relevant WP finds most fitting. The number of stakeholders in these meetings and workshops would expectedly differ depending on the need but also on the availability of stakeholders.

All of the data gathered by ROSIE Work Packages will be used solely for the purposes identified in the ROSIE Description of Action.

2 Fair data

2.1 Making data findable

For the data used for literature review, data will primarily be uploaded in database services provided by the lead institution per WP. After data processing, data will be made findable by

- assigning a globally unique and persistent identifier to (meta)data
- describing data with rich metadata
- including clearly and explicitly in the metadata the identifier of the data it

describes

- register on index (meta)data in a searchable resource
- (meta)data will be uploaded to Zenodo, providing a DOI (Digital Object Identifier) for each dataset generated. Using DOI will allow us to edit/update the record's files after they have been published.

2.2 Making data openly accessible

As mentioned above, ROSiE will gather two types of data from literature review and data from stakeholder inputs. Stakeholder inputs will be directly reflected in relevant reports/publications. No data from stakeholder meetings/workshops will be shared publicly. Project data from literature review will be made accessible via Zenodo. In addition, the libraries created by ROSiE WPs in Zotero will also be made public.

2.3 Making data interoperable

As much as possible,

- (meta)data will use a formal, accessible, shared, and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation.
- (meta)data will use vocabularies that follow FAIR principles
- (meta)data will include qualified references to other (meta)data

2.4 Increase data re-use

On a case by case basis, it will be agreed between all consortium partners when the data produced by the consortium and/or data produced by the engaged citizens will be licensed under Creative Commons, with no embargo to enable re-use. The following guidelines will be followed as much as possible:

- Meta(data) will be richly described with a plurality of accurate and relevant attributes
 - (meta)data will be released with a clear and accessible data usage license
 - (meta)data will be associated with detailed provenance
 - (meta)data will meet domain-relevant community standards.

3 Allocation of resources, data security, and ethics

No additional costs are foreseen since data literature review obtained during the project, when possible, will be uploaded to the free-of-charge Zenodo repository. The handling of the Zenodo repository, as well as all data management issues related to the project, falls in the responsibility of the Coordinator. Since the data are from grey literature and articles, there are no foreseen data security and ethics issues.

